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USE OF TERRESTRIAL LASER SCANNER IN SHORT ROTATION CROPS FOR ABOVE-GROUND WOODY BIOMASS ESTIMATION

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ABSTRACT

Short-rotation crops (SRC) have become an important source of woody biomass around the world [1, 2]. The expansion of the SRC is supported by environmental policies and economic considerations: wood for cellulose or biomass for energy [3]. A precise estimate of biomass production is necessary for the sustainable planning of forest resources and for the exchange of energy in ecosystems. The use of the terrestrial laser scanner (TLS) in estimating the production of above ground wood biomass (AGWB) of short rotation crops brings an important technological leap among indirect (non-destructive) methods. TLS technology is justified when destructive methods become difficult to carry out and allometric equations do not give accurate information [4]. The main purpose is to estimate the biomass productivity on tree parts in short rotation forestry with TLS technology, comparing the results with the gravimetric method. Measuring the hybrid poplars crops by TLS may have the following consequences: (i) higher accuracy of the estimate of biomass production in the SRC; (ii) cost and time effective measurements over the biomass of tree parts; (iii) new and validated allometric equations for SRC in NE Romania. Through the research protocol, the use of TLS for comparison with the gravimetric method will contribute to the development of knowledge in the field of hybrid crops.

Keywords: above-ground woody biomass (AGWB); short rotation crops (SRC); terrestrial laser scanner (TLS).

INTRODUCTION

The importance of assessment of biomass productivity in short rotation crops (SRC) with terrestrial laser scanner (TLS)

The poplar crops area is growing in Europe, exceeding 800 thousand ha, of which 21% represents systems of short rotation crop production [5, 6]. The system of SRC, is an efficient alternative of bioenergy production under a temperate climate [7, 8].

In Romania, the interest for SRC has increased due to modern cultivation technologies [9, 10]. At the same time, Romania offers a high potential for marginal land suitable for planting of these crops [11, 12], an aspect that has attracted the attention of many investors. Thus, starting with 2009, a private investor has installed significant surfaces of SRC in NE Romania [13, 14]. Currently, in this area are installed more than 800 hectares of SRC. These prospects are particularly of interests to private sector, which finds in short rotation opportunities of developing and investing on short and medium terms.

The right estimation of tree above-ground wood biomass (AGWB) and stem volume is needed both for sustainable planning of forest resources and for optimizing of energy and nutrients flows within terrestrial ecosystems. Moreover, the EU Framework convention on climate change and for the Kyoto Protocol recognize the importance of forest carbon stock in relation to the atmospheric CO₂ concentration [3]. On the other hand, the Romanian policy regarding the "System of tracking wood material" (SUMAL 2.0), is an issue for private investors because for many new hybrid clones there are not any coefficients for a real volume estimation and the *Ministerial Order 1323/2015* (technical rules) does not offer proper volume equation.

Biomass production can be estimated by direct and indirect methods. Recently, the development of terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) has made possible to map a three dimensional plot or a single tree with higher accuracy [15, 16]. The TLS is a technique introduced less than ten years ago as an innovative concept in tree measurement [17, 18].

Using TLS on biomass estimation per tree parts (total, branches and stem) is a topic of great interest for researchers, foresters and private investors. TLS technology is justified when destructive methods become difficult to carry out and allometric equations do not give accurate information.

The goal

The goal of this study is to highlight the potential of TLS technology in above ground wood biomass estimation of hybrid poplar clones in short rotation crops.

The technical point addressed in this paper is to present theoretical aspect of: (i) evaluation of above ground wood biomass using TLS, (ii) assessment of stem quality in short rotation forestry using TLS, and (iii) development of calibrated allometric equations in short rotation crops using TLS technology.

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

Site description

The researchers are carried out in NE Romania in the hilly area (346 m elevation). The climate is temperate continental, with annual temperature of 7°C and rainfall about 550 – 600 mm [19, 20]. The soil is *Faeoziom cambic*, moderately acidic with highly trophic for all selected crops [21, 22]. There are no stational conditions differences between the selected crop areas and have been maintained under the same culture technology [1].

Experimental design

For the most productive hybrid poplar clone (AF8 – *P. x generosa 103-86 x P. trichocarpa PEE* and Pannonia – *P. x euramericana*), three plots for different production cycles ranging from 5 to 7 years are delimited in crops. The size of the plots is approx. 81 m², including approx. 10 trees·plot⁻¹ on two rows, installed for a density of 1667 trees·ha⁻¹ (planting at 3 x 2 m). As planting material are used rods (long cuttings) of 2 m. For the selection of the total 18 sample plots, marginal influence will be avoided (*Table 1*).

Table 18. Characteristics of sample plots

Planting characteristics	Planting density – 3 x 2 m – 1667 trees·ha ⁻¹	
Planting year	2015	2016
Growing seasons (cycle)	6 / 7	5
Inventory stage	2021 / 2022	2021
Plant material	rods – 2 m length	rods – 2 m length
Hybrid poplar clones:	Numbers of sample plots (with approx. 10 trees·plot ⁻¹)	
AF8	3	3
	47°51'19.51"N	47°51'21.40"N
	25°59'13.54"E	25°59'30.23"E
Pannonia	3	3
	47°51'19.67"N	47°50'39.60"N
	25°59'27.52"E	26° 3'40.73"E

The propagating material (rods) was installed in the field at a depth of 0,6 – 0,7 m in the spring of each year in which the installation was made, according to the culture technology adopted [23, 24].

Methods of data collection

Evaluation of above ground wood biomass

TLS scans are carried out beyond the vegetative period, when the hybrid poplars will not present leaves (November – April) in 2021 and 2022 according to inventory stage (*Table 1*). The Z+F Imager 5010 Scanner (Zoller and Fröhlich, Wangen, German) is used to obtain field points clouds, with the necessary additional materials: batteries (or generator), spherical targets (of 200 mm), cables, etc. With the necessary methodological requirements and precautions for practical application [4, 25]. The appropriate weather conditions (with low wind intensity, temperatures more than -10°C and no rain or wet bark) will be monitored to perform scans for the capture of fine branches.

Figure 20. Optimal positioning of TLS, targets and trees in a sample plot. TLS scanning a plot (AF8_16_P1) were spheric targets are used for co-registration to create a 3D point cloud

A minimum of 6 scanning's is used for each plot, with 8 targets of 20 cm (*Figure 1*). The estimated scanning time for a single plot is about 3-4 hours·person⁻¹ (with transport equipment, installation targets, scanning and equipment collecting). Each plot is materialized on the field with metal corner.

All trees within the plots are tagged with numbers and they are measured: stem diameters, heights and crown diameters (for validating equations and checking stem quality). After scanning activities, the destructive method will be used to validate biomass production. For biomass productivity, a series of direct measurements (by weighing) on the green mass on the parts of the trees (total, stem and branches) will be used. According to the working structure presented (*Table 1*), the data are completed in the next vegetative inactive period. Sample plots are scanned, inventoried, harvested and weighed on tree parts, comparing the TLS method with the gravimetric method. Density estimation will be done through the *gravimetric method* in the laboratory, on harvested samples, as follows: wooden rounds from stem and a representative branch [26, 27].

Assessment of stem quality in short rotation forestry using TLS

The quality of the stem will be determined in relation to the Dimensional sorting table (*STAS 1040-85*) and grades needed for wooden boards. The stem will split into two grades: (i) stem log with a minimum diameter of 8 cm at the thin end (used for OSB production), and (ii) wood for biomass (for co-generation) with diameters less than 8 cm [1]. The validation of the distribution on the log assortments will be made by shape indices (using caliper measurements along the tree stem). The defects of wood will also be taken into account.

Allometric equations in short rotation crops using TLS technology

The TLS results will be used to calibrate the allometric equations obtained by destructive methods for the same conditions related to: crops characteristics, area and inputs. For high accuracy of tree parts, it is necessary to generate a model based on the three measurable dendrometric features, including the diameter of the crown (on two perpendicular directions) in addition to the stem diameter and tree height.

Methods of points cloud processing

Data processing involves: co-registration data is carried out on fixed spherical targets (200 mm), filtering data and extracting necessary parameters is done by using *ZF Laser Control*, *CloudCompare*, *R* and *MathLab* software [4]. Long working time, it is necessary for points filtering and error fixing (solving "phantom points"), until tree individual selection (Figure 2). The *Autostem* application (*Treemetrix*) based on multiple scans will determine the stem and branches volume. Volume will be estimated directly from the measurements, while the determination of biomass will require wood density on each part tree [25, 28]. Scanning the branches will be based on a quantitative model taking into account the obstruction [29, 30].

Figure 21. Point cloud selection correspondent of a trees, until their individual materialization. Processing data in *CloudCompare 2.12* (left) and *Z+F LaserControl 9.0.2* (right).

The individual production of AGWB will be extrapolated to the area unit (dry mass $t \cdot ha^{-1}$). The TLS results will be used to calibrate the allometric equations obtained by destructive methods and for the same conditions related to crops characteristics (clone or rotation/ cycle for the same density), area (conditions of vegetation) and inputs.

CONCLUSIONS

In Romania, TLS technology has never been used in short rotation wood crops, the few cases in forest inventories [25, 31]. In this regard, getting fast data at minimal cost became a necessity for stakeholders, especially when this is performed with great accuracy. Compared to the other methods, the use of TLS for biomass (volume) in such crops opens new paths for research. The gain will be both for the scientific side and for the investors in the SRC (economic side). The novelty is the development of the scanning protocol with TLS.

Measuring the hybrid poplars crops by TLS may have the following consequences: *(i)* higher accuracy of the biomass production estimation in the SRF; *(ii)* cost and time effective measurements over the biomass of tree parts; *(iii)* new and validated allometric equations for SRC in NE Romania, and *(iv)* robust instrument for industry to estimate biomass.

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